

A century of flow history and surge analysis of Sít'Tlein (Malaspina Glacier), Southeast Alaska

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Supplementary Materials

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SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES AND LINKS

Figure S1: tracking of points seeded in each tributary between 1984-2022. We use the interpolated velocity dataset averaged for every year.

Figure S2: velocities exceeding the surge threshold along four different transects: one for Agassiz, one for Marvinne, two for Seward.

Figure S3: map of timestamps with the fastest recorded surge-like velocities across the glacier.

Figure S4: zoom on Sít'Tlein's three main tributaries.

Figure S5: plot of the summed fluxes in time for each point along Seward's terminus flux gate.

Figure S6: Zoom on Agassiz's throat to show the folding of its moraines.

Figure S7: zoom on Marvinne's lobe to display the impact of the 1986/87 surge on the terminus.

21 Figure S8: zoom on Seward's terminus to show the stacking of moraines and periglacial lakes.

22 Figure S9: examples of the Landsat "XXF/P" displacement index.

23 Figure S10: maps of the locations where moraines start folding for each tributary.

24 Figure S11: plot of ITS_LIVE velocities of a point in Seward's throat for which we highlight values
25 not overlapping with neighboring values (in time).

26 Figure S12: maps and plots of differences between interpolated and original velocity datasets.

27 Landsat mosaics timelapse: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bX-uHFUtJFQ>

Fig. S1. Spread of straight transects for each tributary, in time. The transects start in 1984 at the orange points. As the ice moves down-glacier and enters the lobes, the geometry imposes a divergence of the ice movement and therefore starts spreading in a fan shape. The points propagate in an unrealistic direction when in slow moving areas (Marvine, Agassiz).

Fig. S2. Surge-like velocities along the flowline of each tributary (values 4 times above the median of each point's timeseries) (see Figure ??).

Fig. S3. Year during which the maximum monthly average velocity of each pixel is occurring, amongst velocities above the velocity (4 time the median) and the time thresholds (4 months per year). Grey/white/black colors represent pixels for which there was no data exceeding both thresholds.

Fig. S4. ITS_LIVE 120m composite map of surface velocities for the three tributaries.

Fig. S5. Scaled fluxes of Seward's terminus, summed in time for each point along the transect. The two groups of peaks correspond roughly to Fountain Stream (first group, 15 km) and Backdoor Lake (second group, 30 km).

Fig. S6. Upper Agassiz lobe. The moraines start oscillating once the flow becomes unconstrained. We can recover past flow information from the way moraines have been displaced.

Fig. S7. 1986/87 surge impact on Marvine's terminus. The red arrows point to the position of the terminus, and the blue line represents the approximate terminus displacement. We estimate it to be roughly 10km.

Fig. S8. Lower Seward lobe. At this place (red arrow), the moraines are stacked together and form a surface of debris-covered ice. That zone marks the transition between dynamic and stagnant ice. South of it the ice is stagnant and covered by vegetation, with a gradient starting at bare rock, then shrubs, and finally mature forests. Backdoor Lake sits at the edge between moraine stacks and vegetation covered ice, while Sít' Kagi Lagoon is entirely in stagnant ice.

Fig. S9. Upper Marvine lobe and its branches. These panels represent the different cases of flow configuration: 21P, 31P, 33P, 33F. The panels labeled 'Start' serve as reference images. If the glacier moves by more than 500 m from one image to the other, the flow is classified as 3. Between 1 and 500 m, classified as 2, and stagnant flow = 1. The letter P or F reflects if the flow propagates further than the middle of the lobe (F) or not (P).

Fig. S10. (a) Gradient of moraine folds increasing from the center to the right side of the Agassiz lobe. (b) Gradient of moraine folds increases from the center to both sides of the Seward lobe. (c) Gradient of moraine folds increases from the center to the left side of the Marvine lobe. They are also elongated by surges coming from the trunks.

Fig. S11. ITS_LIVE errors (red) and their associated velocity magnitudes (black).

Fig. S12. Map of differences between interpolated and original datasets for each velocity component (v_x , v_y), in time and space. The glacier outlines are in black, the colorbar is capped from $-100 m.a^{-1}$ (blue) to $100 m.a^{-1}$ (red) and identical for both components.